

Hypertension Prevention: Stopping the Silent Killer

Adonesse Mavia Francis^{1*} & Adolf Telelen Adietbella²

^{1,2}Texila American University

* Corresponding Author: Adonesse Mavia Francis, Email: adonessefrancis599@gmail.com

APA citation: Adonesse, M.F., & Adolf T.A. (2025). Hypertension Prevention: Stopping the Silent Killer. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 192-195

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 23 Oct 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Essential hypertension DASH diet Hypertensive Normotensive Aerobic exercise</p>	<p>An individual's lifestyle can either play a role in the prevention or the exposure of such a person to certain diseases. Essential hypertension is one of the diseases that are definitely affected by lifestyle choices, particularly diet and exercise. Assuming a clean and healthy dietary approach and including aerobic exercise in one's daily living reduces the chances of developing high blood pressure. It is also important to eliminate risk factors such as tobacco use and high sodium intake as well. Previous studies have shown that a modified diet can lower systolic blood pressure by six to eleven millimeters per mercury, an effect seen in both normotensive and hypertensive patients. This research will provide individuals with concrete evidence that dietary approaches are effective in lowering blood pressure, thereby influencing lifestyle changes worldwide. A review and analysis were conducted using Pub Med and Google scholar. Twelve studies on the DASH diet were included and the result suggests that the DASH diet lowers systolic and diastolic blood pressure by 4.45 mmHg and 2.95 mmHg respectively. As for physical activity, thirteen randomized controlled trials were included. The results suggests that physical exercise lowers systolic and diastolic blood pressure by 9.05 mmHg and 5.84 mmHg respectively. An adaptation of the DASH (Dietary Approach to Stop Hypertension) diet and frequent physical activity will effectively lower blood pressure values, thereby preventing hypertension.</p>

1. Introduction

Essential hypertension is among the world's most common chronic diseases. Its prevalence has prompted numerous research and studies. High blood pressure affects an estimated 26% of the world's population (Alexander, 2019), and so it is not only a health crisis but also a financial strain globally. Commonly called the "silent killer," essential hypertension has no warning signs or symptoms and many people are unaware that they suffer from this particular condition (Mayo Clinic, 2020). The American College of Cardiology/ American Heart Association (Flack et al., 2017) published a new classification scale for blood pressure: 120/80 mmHg (normal), 120-129/>80 (elevated), 130-139 or 80-89 mmHg (stage 1 hypertension or prehypertension) and >140 or >90 mmHg (stage 2 hypertension). Frequent consumption of a diet high in energy dense foods, sodium, fat content, refined carbohydrates, low in fruits and vegetables and added sugar contributes to an increased risk of developing hypertension (Ozemek et al., 2018). Added to the list of risk factors are obesity and the use of tobacco. Hypertension is also associated with the cause of most cardiovascular diseases such as coronary heart disease (CHD), heart failure (HF) and atrial fibrillation. And so, Understanding the domino effect of hypertension leading to even more dangerous diseases should encourage individuals to take actions that will prevent them from developing high blood pressure.

Dietary intervention has been found to lower systolic blood pressure in both hypertensive and normotensive patients (Challa et al., 2020). Individuals whose diets consists of mostly vegetable products have lower blood pressure levels and lower incidence of hypertension than those who ingest regular western pattern diets. This eating plan is called the Dietary Approach to Stop Hypertension (DASH) diet (Juraschek, 2017). This diet is based on an increase in the consumption of vegetables, fruits, whole grains, and low-fat dairy and decrease ingestion of fats, red meats, sodium, and added sugar (Willett & Ludwig, 2020). A typical serving guide for a patient following the DASH diet is as follows: Fruits (about five servings per day), vegetables (about five servings per day), carbohydrates (about seven servings per day), low fat dairy products (about two servings per day), nuts and seeds (two to three times per week), lean meat products (about two or fewer servings per day), (Challa et al., 2020).

Another lifestyle change that has a marked advantage in lowering blood pressure, is regular exercise. Particularly, aerobic exercise decreases blood

pressure, body fat and resting heart rate (Choi et al., 2020). This study investigates the effects of adapting the DASH diet versus regular physical activity on blood pressure. Essential hypertension is particularly associated with poor diets and lack of exercise which results in unhealthy weight. The importance of the effective interventions is discussed by Salicrup et al., (2018). The writers reveal that even though at present there are many proven, effective interventions, the lack of initiation, monitoring and sustenance of their delivery is an issue for these interventions. Therefore, further research on the prevention of hypertension is necessary to educate individuals on the effects of a change in diet on blood pressure. This will encourage the initiation of interventions. In relation to this, many writers focus on reducing sodium intake to prevent high blood pressure. High sodium intake is strongly correlated with the development of hypertension (Taler, 2018). Mayo Clinic (2019) states that reducing dietary sodium can lower blood pressure by approximately 5-6 mmHg. In agreement to this are Larstorp and Tonstad (2016), as they promote the reduction of dietary sodium, adoption of the DASH diet and regular exercise to reduce blood pressure. Lastly, Flack et al., (2017) published a research concerning the non-pharmacological approach to blood pressure reduction. It includes the adoption of a healthy diet, reduction in sodium intake, increased intake of dietary potassium, increase in physical activity, decrease in alcohol consumption and weight loss. This proves that numerous researchers are of the same point of view that diet and exercise play major roles in the prevention and control of hypertension.

A pattern observed in numerous studies is the fact that the sample size decreases overtime. Individuals seem to find it difficult to adhere to the restrictions of the diet or schedule for exercise. Kucharska et al., (2017), carried out a study to assess the impact of individualized nutritional intervention based on the DASH diet (Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension) on the nutritional status, blood pressure, and selected biochemical parameters of obese/overweight patients with primary arterial hypertension. At the end of the research, 92.8% of the intervention group completed the study. Similarly, Tyson et al., (2019) carried out a study on effect the DASH diet has on blood pressure in individuals who suffer from chronic kidney disease. At the end of the study, of 5,306 individuals, only 59% completed it.

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Additionally, in light of the positive effect of the DASH diet on the prevention of hypertension, researchers have recently began exploring its effect on specific racial subgroups. Individuals of African descent are at greater risk of developing hypertension than Caucasians (Fryar et al., 2017). Tyson et al., (2019) express that the DASH diet lowers blood pressure more successfully in blacks in comparison with other racial subgroups. And so, in an effort to reduce this health disparity, it is important to stress the significance of adopting the DASH diet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A review and analysis were conducted using PubMed and Google Scholar for the time period of two thousand and sixteen to two thousand and twenty-one. Twenty-five researches were selected to be studied in detail (n=12,546). Twelve of these are in relation to the effect of the DASH diet on normotensive, prehypertensive and hypertensive patients (n=11,964). The remaining articles pertain to the lowering effects of physical activity on the blood pressure of the previously mentioned groups of individuals (n=582). The following describes the inclusion criteria (Schwingshackl et al., 2018): randomized trial with either a DASH (or DASH-like) diet, an intervention period of at least 4 weeks, normotensive, prehypertensive or hypertensive adults and an investigation into both diastolic and systolic blood pressure. As for the trials for physical activity, this was restricted to regular aerobic or medium intensity exercise. The following studies were excluded

(Schwingshackl et al., 2018): randomized trials including pregnant women, randomized trials including patients who are also taking antihypertensive drugs and studies that investigated only systolic blood pressure. After determination of the study selection, the analyst extracted the following characteristics: year of publication, name of first author, sample size and the mean decrease in systolic and diastolic blood pressure. The mean of the obtained data for systolic and diastolic blood pressure was calculated for both the DASH diet and those on the effects of physical activity on blood pressure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The characteristics of twenty-five studies that were included in the systematic review are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2. These studies were conducted in the following countries: The United States of America (five studies), Japan (four studies), Australia (one study), Sweden (one study), Poland (one study), Canada (three studies), Greece (one study), Pakistan (one study), Iran (one study), Amsterdam (one study), China (one study), Spain (three studies) and The Netherlands. Overall, the trials involved 12,546 participants. All twenty-five studies recruited both male and female participants. The researches were published between 2016 and 2020. The study length of the trials included range between three and forty-eight months.

Reference	Country	No. Participants	Decrease in systolic pressure (mmHg)	Decrease in diastolic pressure (mmHg)
Chiavaroli et al., 2019	Canada	65	5.2	2.6
Chiu et al., 2016	United States of America	36	4.8	3.7
Edwards et al., 2020	United States of America	39	4.7	3.3
Jenkins et al., 2017	Canada	145	3.5	2.4
Juraschek et al., 2017	United states of America	412	6	5
Kucharska et al., 2017	Poland	131	4.63	2.64
Mahdavi et al., 2021	Iran	20	0.48	0.48
Naseem et al., 2016	Japan	1492	2.197	0.118
Selvaraj et al., 2017	United States of America	2,996	5	2
Spence, 2018	Canada	15	5.3	3.7
Tsioufis et al., 2020	Greece	5,545	4.2	3.5
Zafarmand et al., 2019	Amsterdam	1068	7.2	6

Table 1: Summary of characteristics and results from twelve studies that investigate the effect of the DASH diet on blood pressure.

The mean for the decrease in systolic blood pressure was calculated and found to be 4.43 mmHg, while the decrease in diastolic blood pressure was found to be 2.95 mmHg. Previous studies have similar results. The most similar being from a study conducted by Kucharska et al., (2017). A three

months long nutritional interventional study was carried out to investigate the impact of individualized nutritional therapy according to the DASH diet on blood pressure.

Reference	Country	No. Of Participants	Decrease in systolic pressure (mmHg)	Decrease in diastolic pressure (mmHg)
Borjesson et al., 2016	Sweden	27	11	5
Choi et al., 2020	China	27	5.5	5
Costa et al., 2019	Brazil	20	7.9	6.7
Kawabe et al., 2019	Japan	62	11	7
Kawamura et al., 2016	Japan	60	14	11
Kleinnibbelink et al., 2020	Netherlands	21	9	5
Lison et al., 2020	Spain	50	13.5	9
Liu et al., 2020	Spain	105	13.5	9.1
Michishita et al., 2017	Japan	78	11.1	7.8
Pedralli et al., 2020	United States of America	42	4	3.2
Rodrguez et al., 2017	Spain	23	12	6
Wheeler et al., 2019	Australia	67	5.1	1.1

Table 2: Summary of characteristics and results for thirteen randomized controlled trials that investigate the effect of physical exercise on blood pressure.

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The mean for the decrease in systolic blood pressure was calculated and found to be 9.05 mmHg while for diastolic blood pressure was found to be 5.84 mmHg. A previous study, conducted by Kleinnibbelink *et.al.*, (2020)

has found similar data. A twelve-weeks long exercise training program was conducted to investigate the BP lowering effects of physical activity.

Figure 1: Showing a comparison between the DASH diet and Physical activity, using the mean values calculated for the decrease in systolic and diastolic blood pressure.

As per figure 1, the mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure for the physical activity intervention is greater compared to the values obtained for the DASH diet. Values obtained from studies in table 1 and table 2 support this pattern. These values suggest that physical activity has a greater impact on the lowering of blood pressure than dietary intervention. This analysis of 25 studies including 12,546 participants, compare the effects of the DASH diet versus physical activity in lowering blood pressure. The results obtained are consistent with previous studies conducted primarily in the United States of America. A significant reduction of 4.45 mmHg in systolic blood pressure and 2.95 mmHg in diastolic blood pressure was observed in the present analysis for the DASH diet. Dietary modification represents a promising prevention for numerous chronic health issues, including hypertension. The DASH diet in particular, has been a benchmark for the dietary requirements that have blood pressure lowering effects. It consists primarily of fruits and vegetables, whole grains, low-fat dairy, seeds, nuts and legumes with low intake of meats and saturated fats (Ndanuko *et.al.*, 2016). This diet has been adopted in numerous countries worldwide. On the other hand, a greater decrease in systolic and diastolic blood pressure is observed for the effects of physical activity on blood pressure. The results obtained are 9.05 mmHg (systolic blood pressure) and 5.84 mmHg (diastolic blood pressure). The difference between the values obtained for these two interventions is quite significant.

The DASH diet is widely considered as on the most effective dietary interventions for the reduction of blood pressure in both hypertensive and prehypertensive patients (Fu *et.al.*, 2020). The results obtained in this study supports this pattern. This suggests that a compliant patient who follows the daily requirements of the DASH diet can effectively prevent themselves from developing hypertension. From the data retrieved, the greatest decrease in systolic and diastolic blood pressure are 7.2 mmHg and 6.2 mmHg respectively (Zafarmand *et.al.*, 2019). This indicates that the DASH diet has the potential to lower blood pressure even more significantly than this present analysis observes. These results are of utmost importance in today's society. A simple change in diet can prevent individuals from enduring an incurable and potentially fatal illness. However, 13% of the world's population is obese and 39% is overweight (WHO, 2020). Obesity, in particular the excessive abdominal fat distribution, is accompanied by several changes at the hormonal, endothelial and inflammatory level. These alterations influence a stimulation of multiple other mechanisms that contribute to the hypertensive state (Seravalle & Grassi 2017). And so, it is important for individuals to know that the prevention of hypertension and maintaining a healthy BMI are major advantages of adopting the dietary requirements of the DASH diet: Fruits (about five servings per day),

vegetables (about five servings per day), carbohydrates (about seven servings per day), low fat dairy products (about two servings per day), nuts and seeds (two to three times per week), lean meat products (about two or fewer servings per day), (Challa *et.al.*, 2020).

The present analysis observes that physical activity has an enormous blood pressure lowering effect. The values obtained are 9.05 mmHg (systolic blood pressure) and 5.84 mmHg (diastolic blood pressure). Exercises that are aerobic in nature have been found to lower blood pressure levels quite significantly (Boutcher & Boutcher 2017). Regular aerobic exercise works to lower blood pressure by strengthening the muscles of the heart (Mayo Clinic, 2019). A stronger heart can pump more blood with less effort. And so, the force on the arteries decreases, thereby lowering blood pressure. Additionally, like the DASH diet, physical activity is also effective in the maintenance of a healthy weight which is very important to the prevention of hypertension.

Conclusion

This analysis observes that both the DASH diet and physical activity have significant effects on the lowering of blood pressure. The data obtained suggest that physical activity has a greater effect, thus lowering both systolic and diastolic blood pressure more significantly than the DASH diet. The findings of the present analysis have important clinical and public health implications. Suggesting that physical activity, particularly aerobic exercise and the consumption of vegetables, fruits, whole grains, and low-fat dairy and decrease ingestion of fats, red meats, sodium, and added sugar are significant lifestyle changes that prevent hypertension.

Funding sources:

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies.

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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